
Lapshin Yevhen, Doctor of Technical Sciences (D.Sc.), Senior Researcher, Principal Researcher in Department Ecology of Natural Resources Development, M.S. Polyakov Institute of Geotechnical Mechanics of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine (IGTM of the NAS of Ukraine), Dnipro, Ukraine, 19481948les@gmail.com, ORCID 0000-0002-5443-5566.

Shevchenko Oleksandr, Doctor of Technical Sciences (D.Sc.), Senior Researcher, Senior Researcher in Department of Geomechanics of Mineral Opencast Mining Technology, M.C. Polyakov Institute of Geotechnical Mechanics of the National Academy of Science of Ukraine (IGTM of the NAS of Ukraine), Dnipro, Ukraine, igtm.aishevchenko@gmail.com, ORCID 0000-0003-2630-0186.

Werner Illia, senior lecturer of the Department of “Construction, Technical Aesthetics and Design”, National Technical University “Dnipro Polytechnic”, Dnipro, Ukraine, verner.i.v@nmu.one

FLY ASH FROM THERMAL POWER PLANTS – A VALUABLE TECHNOGENIC RAW MATERIAL IN THE MANUFACTURING OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS

Annotation. Ash and slag waste are man-made mineral formations that are produced in large quantities and pose a serious environmental hazard. On the other hand, it is a valuable mineral raw material for obtaining various materials. The presented results showed the possibility of extracting useful components (carbon, iron, aluminum, silicates) from fly ash and using them in the manufacture of various composite materials.

Keywords: *composite materials, ash and slag waste, fly ash, extraction of useful components.*

Composite materials (CM) have been known for a long time in human history. Thus, reinforcing marble columns with metal rods was used back in Ancient Greece. The very first industrial composite material is considered to be reinforced concrete, widely used since the end of the 19th century. As is known, composite materials are artificially created materials and consist of two or more chemically different components that differ significantly in properties and are separated by a well-defined intercomponent boundary. They are introduced into the composition of composite materials in order to give them properties that each of the components does not have separately. By changing the size, location, mass and volume ratio of the components, it is possible to obtain materials with the necessary characteristics of physical, mechanical, operational and other properties. Any CM consists of a matrix – a component continuous in the volume of the material, and filler – a discontinuous component in the form of discrete particles of various shapes, placed in it according to a given pattern and united by a matrix. It can perform the functions of both reinforcement (in the CM design) and filler that determines the functional characteristics of the material (thermo physical, electrical, magnetic, tribotechnical, etc.). The scope of application of CM is enormous: aviation technology, astronautics, ships and mechanical engineering, defense industry, energy, construction, medicine, automation, materials for electronics, nanotechnology and much more. The advantages of CM are high strength, heat resistance, and wear resistance. However, their disadvantages should also be

noted: expensive raw materials, production, and cost. Therefore, when creating and manufacturing CM, they strive to reduce the cost of products by using less expensive raw materials, obtained, for example, from man-made waste [1–5].

Every year, in the world, simultaneously with the generation of thermal and electrical energy as a result of the combustion of solid fuel at thermal power plants (TPPs) and combined heat and power plants (CHPs), ash and slag waste (ASW) is generated, which is produced in large quantities and poses a serious environmental hazard, i.e., it creates a global problem. Fuel and energy complex facilities are among the main sources of environmental pollution. The impact of toxic substances contained in ASW storage sites on the environment and the human body is analyzed in [6, 7]. At the same time, man-made waste accumulated over many years has a unique mineral composition and often has a distribution of useful components that is not typical for natural deposits. During the combustion process of fuel, chemical and phase transformations of its mineral substance occur. As a result, substances with new properties are formed – fly ash (the largest type of waste, 75–80% of ASW) and slag. The main components of ASW are oxides: SiO_2 , Al_2O_3 , Fe_2O_3 , CaO , MgO . A small proportion is accounted for by sulfates CaSO_4 , MgSO_4 , FeSO_4 ; phosphates and alkali metal oxides are present in smaller quantities. Ash includes almost all elements of the periodic table of D.I. Mendeleev. The elemental composition of ASW varies greatly depending on the type of coal used, combustion technology and waste disposal. Ash of the same type of coal has different properties, especially from different types of coal. Almost all ashes contain carbon (under burnt) in the form of coke and semi-coke – in the form of either independent particles or inclusions in large fractions of ash.

In industrially developed countries of the world, such as the European Union, the USA and others, the utilization of ASW is an integral part of the technological process of coal thermal power plants, which involves the involvement of various types of waste in new technological cycles or their use for other useful purposes. This problem, which is the most important element in the overall chain of creating waste-free production systems, is given much attention both in our country and abroad [6, 7].

During the recycling process, ASW can be used as secondary raw materials. Based on the analysis of the review of world experience in ASW processing [6, 7], the main areas of their use are: construction (construction products, roofing granules); road works (fillers for road materials and asphalt fillers, etc. Considering the huge volumes and low degree of their utilization in our country, the world experience of ASW processing is useful and very relevant for Ukraine. The search for promising areas of using energy complex waste and new sales markets is an urgent need not only for Ukraine, but for any economically developed state.

The output of ash from Ukrainian TPPs is about 8–10 million tons/year. In the dumps of Ukrainian TPPs, 358.8 million tons of ash and slag have accumulated on an area of about 3,170 hectares. It should be noted that the ashes of coal thermal power plants in Ukraine contain carbon in an amount from 5–7% to 25–30%. The content above 5% does not allow the use of ash in the construction industry in large quantities (for concrete – prohibited by standards) [8, 9]. Therefore, technologies are needed that will provide the opportunity to use ash with a high carbon content to obtain a useful product, or to bring the quality of ash to the indicators required by standards for widespread use in the construction industry.

Fly ash with carbon content corresponding to regulatory requirements is used as a pozzolan for the production of cement, dry building mixtures, partial replacement of Portland cement in the production of concrete, concrete and reinforced concrete products, building materials. In the production of reinforced concrete and concrete mixtures, ash is introduced instead of part of the cement and sand, acting as not only an active mineral additive that increases the total amount of binder, but also micro filler that improves the granulometry of sand and actively influences the processes of concrete structure formation and its quality indicators. The introduction of ash into the concrete mixture, unlike other active mineral additives, generally improves workability, which is explained by the spherical shape of the ash particles, and helps reduce water separation of the concrete mixture. Concrete mixtures with an optimal addition of ash have a fairly high viability and are suitable for transportation over long distances. The use of ash provides greater protection of concrete from humid conditions and the effects of aggressive chemicals, reduces the minimum standard consumption rate of cement and, taking into account its cost, as a consequence, reduces the cost of concrete [6, 7].

Another component of ASW that is in demand by consumers is fly ash microspheres. These are hollow ash balls averaging 20 to 500 μm in size with solid non-porous walls 2 to 10 μm thick, filled with a mixture of nitrogen and carbon dioxide under reduced pressure (about 0.3 at) [10]. Depending on the composition of the coal, the microspheres can be aluminosilicate or Ferro silicate. The latter have pronounced magnetic properties. The unique combination of such qualities of this product as an almost ideal spherical shape, low bulk density, high mechanical strength, thermal stability and chemical inertness, ensured a wide range of applications of cenospheres abroad in the production of thermal insulation materials, radio-transparent ceramics, fillers of composite materials.

Research [10] has established the possibility of extracting useful components (carbon, iron, aluminum, silicates) from fly ash. Ash processing products have a finely dispersed fraction, convenient for further use, which eliminates expensive operations for preparing raw materials. For example, the resulting iron and aluminum powders are suitable for producing parts and units using the pressing method, as well as silicates for molding building structures.

In cases where the carbon content in the ash is higher than the standard values, it is necessary to separate it into its components (carbon-silicates). The results of studies [6, 7, 11–14] indicate the fundamental possibility of obtaining low-ash coal concentrate from TPP fly ash by fine classification by size $-0.2+0.02$ mm with high efficiency for narrow bands of separated classes of dry bulk materials. For these purposes, the M.S. Poliakov Institute of Geotechnical Mechanics of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine (IGTM of the NAS of Ukraine) has created a vibratory impact screen of a new design, which allows for the effective classification of bulk materials by a boundary size of 0.02 mm. These capabilities allowed the separation to produce two products: carbon and silicates (with low carbon content, meeting building code requirements). Carbon is a highly dispersed material that can be used in the production of plastics, elastomers, ceramics; intensely black dyes, varnishes and coatings; synthetic fibers, film materials. The silicate part with low carbon content can be used to manufacture construction products.

It should be noted that fly ash from coal-fired thermal power plants is a valuable potential raw material for the complex extraction of silica, aluminum oxide, iron, as well as many valuable and rare earth metals into commercial products. For example, in foreign literature there is information about the possibility of obtaining: amorphous silica ("white soot"), which is a raw material for "solar silicon" (extraction of SiO_2); commercial alumina (extraction of Al_2O_3); iron concentrate with Fe content above 65% (extraction of Fe_2O_3), including the use of oxides contained in ASW in the manufacture of composite materials. It is possible to obtain liquid glass, wollastonite, metallic gallium, vanadium pentoxide. This experience is useful and relevant for Ukraine, so specialists should study it, and this direction can be the subject of further research in this area.

References

1. Vyshnyakov L. R. Composite materials. Encyclopedia of Modern Ukraine. Kyiv: Institute of Encyclopedic Research of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine, 2014.
2. Evans A., San Marchi C., Mortensen A. Metal Matrix Composites in Industry. Dordrecht; Boston; London, 2003.
3. Chawla K. K. Ceramic Matrix Composites. Boston; Dordrecht; London, 2003.
4. Kopan V. S. Compositional materials: teaching. manual Kyiv: Pulsary. 2004. 196 p.
5. Burya O. I. Polymer composites: preparation, properties, application. Dnipropetrovsk: Fedorchenko A. A. 2010. 383 p.
6. Lapshin Ye. S., Shevchenko O. I., Khayitov O. G. Foreign experience of processing ash slag waste from thermal power plants. *Geotekhnicheskaya mekhanika* [Geotechnical Mechanics]. 2024. No 168. P. 105–120.

7. Lapshin Ye. S., Shevchenko O. I., Khayitov O. G. Processing of ash waste from thermal power plants: foreign experience and ukrainian realities. *Geotekhnicheskaya mekhanika* [Geotechnical Mechanics]. 2024. No 169 . P.

8. Dovgopolo V. N. Dalsica™ systems gasify ash from coal-fired power plants. Products – energy carriers, binders for the construction industry and sorbents for purifying gases from the coal power industry, metallurgy, and housing and communal services. *Akademiya budivnitstva Ukraïni: Zhurnal «Budivnitstvo. Nauka. Proyehti. Yekonomika*. [Academy of Life Sciences of Ukraine: Magazine “Business Life Sciences. The science. Projecti. Economics]. 2012. No 31. P. 1-19. Accessed: https://gazobeton.org/sites/default/files/sites/all/uploads/tehnologiya_%20dlya_izvesti.pdf

9. Dolgopolo V. N. Quickly payback and highly profitable productions of the construction industry with guaranteed provision and unlimited sales. *Programs and example of the project. Science. Projects. Economy*. Publication of the Academy of Construction of Ukraine. 2014. No 1. P. 1-9. Accessed: https://gazobeton.org/sites/default/files/sites/all/uploads/2014_1_Article_Acad_9pg.pdf

10. Demchenko V. Export-import potential of ash microspheres in Ukraine. *Goods and markets*. 2016. №2. C. 31-38.

11. Nadutyi V. P., Kostyrya S. V. and Sevastyanov V. S. Justification of the feasibility of complex processing of fly ash from thermal power plants. *Geotekhnicheskaya Mekhanika* [Geo-Technical Mechanics]. 2016. No. 131. P. 59-66. Available at: <http://dspace.nbu.gov.ua/bitstream/handle/123456789/138772/06-Nadutyi.pdf?sequence=1>

12. Nadutyi V. P., Shevchenko A. I. and Khmelenko I. P. Processing of fly ash from thermal power plants. *Geotekhnicheskaya Mekhanika* [Geo-Technical Mechanics]. 2007 No 68. P. 82-87. Available at: <http://geotm.dp.ua/index.php/uk/collection/605-geotekhnichna-mekhanika-2007/geo-technical-mechanics-2007-68>

13. Lapshin E. S., Shevchenko A. I. Ways of improvement of vibrational segregation and dehydration of mineral raw materials. *Naukovyi Visnyk Natsionalnoho Hirnychoho Universytetu*. 2013. №3. C. 45-51.

14. Shevchenko O. I. Analysis of the influence of the size of particles on the choice of constructive and mode parameters of the vibro-impact screen during dehydration and separation of technogenic raw materials. *Geotekhnicheskaya mekhanika* [Geotechnical Mechanics]. 2021. No 159. P. 69-78.